

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Shamloo and Kent, 2024, *Volcanica*, <https://doi.org/10.30909/vol.07.01.123xx>

Supplemental Figure 1. Crystallinity with silica content of the 888 samples with available SiO₂ data and grouped by compilation source. The Marsh (1981) dataset includes 57 samples, Brophy (1991) includes 512 samples, Scaillet (1998) includes 37 samples, Takeuchi (2011) includes 81 samples, and 201 samples compiled for “this study” from a range of references reported in Data Compilation File.

Supplemental Figure 2. Total alkali-silica (TAS) diagram of the samples with available major element data (n=280). Data is grouped by whole rock (squares) or glass (circles) and color coated by crystallinity value. Note, the majority of the samples are subalkaline.

Supplemental Figure 3 A.) The distribution of crystallinities grouped by eruptive style/sample type including the Brophy (1991) compilation but assuming they are all lava samples. Bin size was determined using Sturges rule, which gives values from 7-10 for each panel. A bin size of 10 was chosen so each panel would have an identical bin size. A kernel density estimate is also included to verify that the choice of bin size does not affect the overall distribution shape (solid line). The dashed vertical line marks the average crystallinity of each distribution. B.) Cumulative distribution function (CDF) of each eruptive style. The 5th and 95th percentile values for the distributions for lava, dome, tephra, and ignimbrites are 1 and 54 vol.%, 7 and 78 vol.%, 4 and 53 vol.%, and 3 and 51 vol.%.

Supplemental Figure 4. Crystallinity with silica content of the 376 samples with available SiO₂ data (excluding Brophy (1991) dataset) both as whole rock and glass, and grouped by eruptive style including lava, dome, tephra, and ignimbrite. Dashed line is the linear regression from Marsh (1981), and solid labeled lines are linear regressions for each subset of data. Values that accompany linear regressions can be found in Table 1.

Supplemental Figure 5. Crystallinity with silica content grouped by tectonic settings including subduction (A), rift zone (B), and intraplate (C), following the classification of the Global Volcanism Program (<https://volcano.si.edu/>) including the Brophy (1991) dataset. The dashed line in panel A represents the linear regression determined by Marsh (1981) with an R^2 value of 0.7 and parameters reported in Table 1 in the main text. The solid line is the linear regression for the dataset with corresponding values reported in Table 1 in main text also. The histogram on the bottom shows the frequency of data over a range of silica contents sampled. Bins were chosen at 10 based on Sturges rule so each panel would have an identical bin size. A kernel density estimate is also included to verify that the choice of bin size does not affect the overall distribution shape (solid line over histogram). The color scheme corresponds with SiO_2 content, where dark colors are low SiO_2 , and lighter colors are high SiO_2 .